

MODERN ASPECTS OF MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE HEART UNDER LOCAL AND GENERAL ANESTHESIA

Turnieзов Azamat Askarovich

Bukhara State Medical Institute

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Accurate and correct description of morphological changes in the myocardium in experimental animals is of great importance for understanding the pathogenesis, the mechanism of the relationship between changes in structure and function. The heart is located in the thoracic cavity and is almost completely surrounded by the lungs and is free only in the anterior-inferior region. Heart rate and rhythm are regulated by the autonomic and endocrine systems, hemodynamic factors [15]. Blood supply to the heart is carried out by the left and right coronary arteries; they do not have numerous collaterals. The left coronary artery passes in the groove between the left atrium and the pulmonary artery, intramyocardially. Rats do not have a true circumflex artery of the heart [3].

Cardiac fibroblasts, cardiomyocytes, endothelial cells and vascular smooth muscle cells are the main cellular components of the heart. Cardiomyocytes in the myocardium of rats are located in the form of tightly packed parallel bundles or in bundles with different orientations. Atrial cardiomyocytes are smaller in area and more freely located. The myocardium of rats is mainly represented by binuclear cardiomyocytes [11]. Structural changes in the rat heart associated with age are characterized by a decrease in the number of cardiomyocytes, the development of left ventricular hypertrophy, and a change in the diameter of the ventricular chambers. Left ventricular hypertrophy in rats is caused by interstitial fibrosis [20].

Cardiac hypertrophy. An increase in the mass and size of the heart can be associated with amyloid deposition, proliferation of connective tissue, edema, infiltration by cellular elements, an increase in the size of myocytes (volume, length and thickness, area). Cardiomyelia can be local or diffuse; the cytoplasm of enlarged cardiomyocytes is hypereosinophilic with huge hyperchromic nuclei, often combined with fibrosis in the myocardium [5]. Dystrophy, apoptosis and necrosis of cardiomyocytes. 1. Hyaline drop dystrophy - hyaline-like protein droplets appear in the cytoplasm of cardiomyocytes, merging with each other and filling the cell body, while the ultrastructural elements of the cell are destroyed. It is rare in the human myocardium [11]. 2. Hydropic dystrophy - is characterized by the appearance of vacuoles in the cytoplasm of cardiomyocytes. Hyaline drop dystrophy and hydropic dystrophy often represent successive stages of cytoplasmic protein metabolism disorders depending on the predominance of denaturation and coagulation or hydration and colliquation of the cytoplasm [11]. Hyaline drop dystrophy was diagnosed in the myocardium of rats in experiments with an overdose of catecholamines [13]. Hydropic dystrophy was noted in the myocardium of rats with the introduction of doxorubicin [10]. Apoptosis of cardiomyocytes is manifested by changes in the nucleus - chromatin margination (condensation of chromatin along the periphery of the nucleus in the form of hemispheres or lumps), chromatin condensation (manifested by pycnosis of the nucleus), uneven contours (the nucleus acquires a lobed appearance with disintegration into micronuclei); changes in the cytoplasm - changes in staining (basophilia in the early stages and eosinophilia at the stage of apoptotic bodies), vacuolization (develops due to dilation of the smooth endoplasmic reticulum), changes in contours and fragmentation (indentations and protrusions appear on

the cell surface, after which the cell disintegrates) [5]. With the combined administration of ephedrine and caffeine, both apoptosis and necrosis of cardiomyocytes were detected in the myocardium of rats [16].

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